

Hive Big Data Table Performance Tuning Techniques

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Jan 2021

Abstract: Hive table in Big data plays significant role in generating reports, data analytics and feeding data to Machine learning and Artificial Intelligence. The data in hive table needs to be organized and consolidated for optimization of query performance.

Keywords: Hive table, Big data, Performance Tuning of Hive big data, Hive data analytics & Reporting.

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Introduction

Hive table is one of the big data tables which relies on structural data. By default, it stores the data in a hive warehouse. To store at a specific location, the developer can set the location using a location tag during the table creation. Hive follows the same SQL concepts like row, columns, and schema.

Developers working on big data applications have a prevalent problem when reading Hadoop file systems data or hive table data.

The data is written in Hadoop clusters using spark streaming or Nifi streaming jobs or any streaming or ingestion application. When these apps write data in the Hadoop cluster in the Hadoop file system and known as Hdfs or Hive tables, lot of small data files are written in the Hadoop Cluster.

These part files are written across different data nodes, and when the number of files increases in the directory, it becomes tedious and a performance bottleneck while some other app or user tries to read this data. One of the reasons is that data is distributed across nodes. Think about your data residing in multiple distributed nodes. The more scattered it is, the job takes around “N * (Number of files)” time to read data, where N is the number of nodes across each Name Nodes. For example, if there are 1 million files, when we run MapReduce job, the mapper has to run for 1 million files across data nodes and this will lead to full cluster utilization leading to performance issues.

For beginners, the Hadoop cluster comes with several Name Nodes, and each Name Node will have multiple Data Nodes. Ingestion/Streaming jobs write data across multiple data nodes, and it has performance challenges while reading those data. The job which reads the data will take a considerable time for developers to figure out the problem associated with query response time. This problem mostly

occurs for clients whose data is in 100's of millions in volume every day. For smaller datasets, this performance technique may not be necessary, but it is always good to do some additional tuning for the long run. I'll discuss how to tackle these problems in this article.

Let's first look at some use cases of Hive data usage.

Use Cases

Hive data is predominantly used in the following applications:

- Big Data Analytics, running analytics reports on transaction behavior, activity, volume, and more.
- Track fraudulent activity and generate reports on this activity.
- Create dashboards based on the data.
- Auditing purposes and a store for historical data.
- Feeding data for Machine learning and building intelligence around it.

Tuning Techniques

There are several ways to ingest data into Hive tables. Ingestion can be done through Apache Spark streaming job or Nifi or any streaming technology or application. The data which gets ingested is raw data, and it's very important to consider all tuning factors before the ingestion process begins.

Organizing Hadoop Data

The first step is how to organize Hadoop data. We begin with ingestion/streaming jobs. First, the data needs to be partitioned. The most basic way to partition data is by day or hourly, or it is even worth sometimes to have two partition days and hours. In some cases, you can partition within a day by some country, region, or something that fits your data and use case. For example, think about a library shelf, where books are arranged based on genre, and each genre is set in a child or adult section.

Figure 1: Data Organized

So, we take this example, we write data in Hadoop directory like –

```
hdfs://cluster-uri/app-path/category=children/genre=fairytale OR  
hdfs://cluster-uri/app-path/category=adult/genre=thrillers
```

So, in this way your data is more organized.

In most common case, data is partitioned by day or hour in case of no specific use-cases

hdfs://cluster-uri/app-path/day=20191212/hr=12

or just a day partition depending on requirement. hdfs://cluster-uri/app-path/day=20191212.

Figure 2: Ingestion Flow

Hadoop Data format

When creating a hive table, it is good to provide table compress properties like zlib and format like orc. And while ingesting, these data will be written in these formats. If your application is writing in plain Hadoop file systems, it is advised to provide the format. Most of the ingestion frameworks like Spark or Nifi have a way to specify the format. Specifying the data format helps make the data more organized in a compressed format which saves space in the Cluster.

Consolidation Job

Consolidation job plays a crucial role in improving the performance of the overall read of Hadoop data. There are several parts associated with the consolidation technique. By default, the files written in hdfs directories are small part files and when having too many part files will have performance issues while reading the data. Consolidation is not any particular feature of hive, it is a technique used to merge smaller files to bigger files.

What is a consolidation job?

By default, ingestion/streaming jobs writing to Hive, directories write into small part files, and in a day for high volume applications, these files will be more than 100,000+ depending on volume. The real problem comes when we try to read the data, it takes a lot of time, sometimes several hours, to eventually return the result or the job can fail. For instance, let's assume you have a day partition directory, and you need to process around 1 million small files. For example, if run count:

Before:

```
hdfs dfs -count -v /cluster-uri/app-path/day=20191212/* Output = 1Million
```

Now, after running the consolidation job, the number of files will be reduced significantly. It merges all small part files into large size files.

After:

```
hdfs dfs -count -v /cluster-uri/app-path/day=20191212/* Output = 1000
```

How Consolidation Job Helps

Consolidation of files is essential not just for performance sake but also for cluster healthiness. As per Hadoop platform guidelines, there should not be so many files lying in the nodes. Having too many files will cause too many nodes to read and attribute to high latency. Remember, when to read hive data, it scans across all data nodes. If you have too many files, then read time spreads accordingly. So, it is essential to merge all those small files into bigger files. Also, it is necessary to have purge routines if data is not needed after certain days.

How Consolidation Works

There are several ways to do the consolidation of files. It mainly depends on where you are writing the data. Below I will discuss different common use cases.

- Writing data using Spark or Nifi to hive table in daily partition folder.
- Writing data using Spark or Nifi to Hadoop file system (HDFS)

Here, in this case, huge files would be written in the daily folder. Developer needs to follow any below options.

Figure 3: Consolidation Logic

- a) Write a script to perform the consolidation. The script takes parameters like day and perform hive select data from same partition data and insert overwrite in the same partition. Here, when Hive re-writes data in the same partition, it runs a map reduce job and reduces the number of files.
- b) Sometimes, overwriting the same data in the same command may leave us with unexpected data loss if the command fails. In this case, select the data from the daily partition and write in a temporary partition. If it is successful, then move the temporary partition data to the actual partition using the load command. This step is illustrated in Figure 3.

Between these two options, option B is better, which fits all the use-cases and most efficient. Option B is efficient because there is no data loss if any step fails. Developers can write a control m and schedule to run at next day around midnight, when there are no active users reading data.

There is one use case where the developer needs not to write a hive query. Instead, submit a spark job and select the same partition and overwrite the data, but this is recommended only when the number of files not huge in the partition folder and spark can still read the data without over-specifying resources. This option fits for low volume use cases, and this extra step can boost the performance of reading the data.

How does the entire flow work?

Let's take one example use-case to go over all the pieces.

Assume you own an e-commerce app, you have the process to track daily customer volume by different purchasing categories. Your app is very high volume and you need a smart data analytics set up based on customer purchasing habits and history.

From the presentation layer to the mid-tier layer, you want to publish these messages using [Kafka](#) or [IBM MQ](#). The next piece is to have one streaming app that consumes Kafka/MQ and ingests into Hadoop Hive tables. Through Nifi or Spark, this can be achieved. Before doing this, the Hive table needs to be designed and created. During the Hive table creation, you need to decide what's your partition column looks like and any sorting required and compression algorithm like [Snappy](#) or [Zlib](#) needed to be applied.

The Hive table design is a crucial aspect of determining overall performance. One must consider how data is going to be queried based on that design has to be applied. If we want to query daily how many customers had purchased items in a particular category like Toys, Furniture, etc., it is advisable to have two partitions at most, like a day partition and one as a category partition. The streaming app should then ingest the data accordingly.

Having all the usability aspects beforehand gives us better chances of designing tables to suit our needs. So once data is ingested into this table, data should be organized within day and category partition for the above example.

Only ingested data will be small files in hive location, so as explained above, it becomes vital for us to consolidate those files.

As the next part of your process, you can set up a scheduler or use a control M to run a daily consolidation job nightly, like around 1 AM, which will call the consolidation scripts. Those scripts will consolidate the data for you. Finally, in those hive locations, you should see the number of files reduced.

When the real smart data analytics runs for the previous day, it will be easy to query with better performance.

Technical Implementation

Now, let's take one use case example and show step by step. Here I am considering ingesting customer

events data into the Hive table. My downstream systems or team will further use this data to run analytics like in a day what all items did customer purchase and from which city. This data will be used to analyze the demographics of my product used, which will allow me to troubleshoot or expand business use cases. This data can further enable us to understand where my active customer is from and how I can do more to increase my business.

Step 1: Create a sample Hive table. Here is the code snippet.

```
CREATE DATABASE IF NOT EXISTS CUSTOMER

CREATE EXTERNAL TABLE customer_click_events (
  customerid bigint,
  name string,
  lastUpdatedActivity string,
  isProductPurchase boolean,
  purchasedProductName string,
  city string
) PARTITIONED BY(day string)
  STORED AS ORC LOCATION '/data/customevents/'
  TBLPROPERTIES('orc.bloom.filter.columns'='*', 'orc.compress'='ZLIB');
```

Step 2: Set up a streaming job to ingest into Hive table.

This streaming job can spark streaming from Kafka real-time data and then transform and ingest it into the hive table.

Figure 4: Hive Data Flow

So when live data is ingested, the data will be written in day partition. Let's assume today's date is 20200101
hdfs dfs -ls /data/customevents/day=20200101/

```
/data/customevents/day=20200101/part0000-djwhu28391
/data/customevents/day=20200101/part00001-gjwhu28e92
/data/customevents/day=20200101/part00002-hjwhu28342
/data/customevents/day=20200101/part00003-dewhu28392
/data/customevents/day=20200101/part00004-dfdhu24342
/data/customevents/day=20200101/part00005-djwhu28fdf
/data/customevents/day=20200101/part00006-djwffd8392
/data/customevents/day=20200101/part00007-ddfdggg292
so on.
```

By the End of the day, depending upon traffic of your application, the number could be around anywhere between

10K to 1M. For large scale companies the volume will be high. Let's assume the total number of files was 141K.

Step 3: Running consolidation job

On 2020-01-02, i.e., the next day, around 1 AM, now we should run the consolidation job. The sample code is uploaded in git. The file name is consolidation.sh.

Below is command to run in your edge node/box
./consolidate.sh 20200101

This script will now consolidate previous day data. After it finished, you can rerun the count

```
hdfs dfs -count -v /data/customerevents/day=20200101/* count = 800
```

So, before it was 141K, and after consolidation, the count is 800. So, this will give significant performance benefit.

Link for consolidation logic code: <https://github.com/skoloth/Hive-Consolidation>

Statistics

Without applying any tuning technique, the query time to read Hive table data will take anywhere between 5 Mins to several hours depending upon volume.

After consolidation, query time significantly reduces, and we get results faster. The number of files will be significantly reduced and query time to read the data will decrease. Without consolidation, queries run on so many small files which spread across the name nodes and lead to increase in response time.

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